

Deliverable D6.1 - Dissemination and Communication plan, and visual identity

WP6 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Version 0.0.4 November 2023

(Grant Agreement 101094014)

HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-02-01- Blueprint demonstration for co-created effective, efficient and resilient networks of MPAsclimate resilience

Document History

Deliverable Title	Dissemination and Communication plan, and visual identity
Brief Description	WP6 aims to ensure the effective dissemination and uptake of BLUE4ALL outputs and results to targeted audiences, including entities external to the consortium. It creates project's visual identity, maximizes the project's visibility and spread pertinent information on Blue Park goals.
WP number	6
Lead Beneficiary	All
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Deliverable Due Date	30/06/2023
Actual Delivery Date	05/09/2023
Nature of the Deliverable	R – Report;
Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Approved by	
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Deliverable number	6.1

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
GA	Grant Agreement
LMS	Learning Management System
M	Month
NGO	Non-governmental organization
TG	Target Group
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

The BLUE4ALL Communication and Dissemination Plan (Deliverable D6.1) describes the specific activities and presents the detailed timeline related to outreach and to the dissemination of the results and knowledge generated in the project. The communication plan defines various actions and communication channels which are tailored to the needs of different interested target groups, outlines the strategy for communication and dissemination, and provides communication material.

2. Introduction and overall strategy

The communication and dissemination plan is a reference document which describes the strategy and the specific activities for outreach and for the effective communication and dissemination of the results and knowledge generated within the BLUE4ALL project for various target groups, including the definition of key target groups and the main communication channels identified to reach them. The plan is designed to be flexible and adaptive and will be shaped by the information and results as they are achieved during the project lifetime as reported in future updates.

The BLUE4ALL communication and dissemination plan relies on a strategy that aims to spread information on the project outside the consortium members, focusing on potential users in different countries interested in the project outputs. The communication strategy also aims to inform the media and the general public about the main project results, describing the potential for the innovative contributions of the project for the scientific community, climate services providers, and the relevant stakeholders and policymakers.

To achieve its objectives, the communication strategy foresees the development and application of a series of tools and activities designed to:

- Capitalise on the multidisciplinary nature of the actors involved in the project both as partners and as stakeholders (including universities, European Union agencies, decision-makers, policymakers, non-governmental organisations, industry, and all potentially interested stakeholders);
- Activate the dialogue between stakeholders and the scientific community to (i) define, promote, and implement a fruitful exchange of information and data regarding the most advanced scientific knowledge and (ii) support interactions among the different players and actors focusing on the needs and requirements of the end-users;
- Maximise the impact of the project and prepare and support the exploitation of the results by the different target groups;
- Ensure the continuous availability of information and data regarding the BLUE4ALL research outcomes for local stakeholders and end-users in the three sample countries (Germany, Romania and Spain).

The BLUE4ALL communication activities will involve all consortium partners. This concerted approach is the basis of the communication strategy for at least two reasons. First, consortium-wide communication activities allow capitalising on each partner's network and specific field of expertise (including networking and communications with peer institutions and researchers, stakeholders or research projects) as well as their respective focus geographical area. Second, this approach enables the maximum involvement of stakeholders and interested target groups. Furthermore, it ensures a comprehensive and integrated representation of the research developed by the project, the results obtained, and the positive impacts of the latter on society.

The Communication section of this document details the actions and channels for effective communication. All these activities are tailored to the target groups, accounting for differences across key levers and assistance measures in Germany, Romania and Spain, as well as the diverse interests of local stakeholders, policymakers, and the international scientific community.

Defining the target audience is essential to produce impact outside the BLUE4ALL consortium. Therefore, the formats, language, and focus of the communication material and activities are conceived and will be further shaped to address the specificities of the identified target groups.

3. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION OVERVIEW

3.1. Communication and Dissemination Actions

The main communication and dissemination actions are the following:

- Design an effective communication and dissemination strategy for the project;
- Identify effective communication channels to the project's stakeholders, the scientific community, and broader audiences;
- Create communication and dissemination materials and establish a project website;
- Communicate the project activities and disseminate the project outputs to the various stakeholders and local communities of the case study regions and related audiences, and support know-how transfer at the local level;
- Communicate the project activities, disseminate the project outputs, and support know-how transfer at the international level, exploiting the various scientific and business networks of the project partners, conferences and social media channels;
- Implement a publicly accessible platform for the dissemination of project results to a broad audience.

3.2. Communication and Dissemination Deliverables

The following table identifies the primary communication and dissemination deliverables, as well as important stakeholder events. These events will be documented and accompanied by adequate communication activities, in addition to the continuous communication and dissemination activities described in this document.

Table 1 Primary communication and dissemination deliverables.

Deliverable	Communication & dissemination deliverables	Month
D6.1	Dissemination and communication plan and Visual identity	M6
D6.2	First dissemination and communication report	M24
D6.3	Knowledge transfer and awareness raising along the MPA Networks- Key results and recommendations	M46
D6.4	Exploitation plan	M44
D6.5	Second dissemination and communication report	M46

4. VISUAL IDENTITY AND COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

The following section describes the project logos (Section 4.1) text and presentation templates (Section 4.2) which have been developed for the communication and dissemination activities and which the consortium will be required to use to guarantee a common visual identity.

4.1. BLUE4ALL Visual Identity and Logo

The colours of the logos use the palette illustrated in Figure 1; additional versions were designed using only blue, and white colours, respectively. The font used in the logo is Roboto which font family is free and available from <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Roboto>.

Figure 1 BLUE4ALL logo: (left) primary version, (right) secondary version

4.2. BLUE4ALL Templates

BLUE4ALL templates for presentations and deliverables are presented here and their visual design was informed by the BLUE4ALL corporate design, shown below.

4.3. BLUE4ALL Presentations

The presentation template (Figure 2) will be used not only for internal communication at project meetings and reviews, but also for the communication and dissemination of project results to external target groups both at the international and local levels, e.g. to scientific communities at conferences and workshops, local BLUE4ALL stakeholders, and the general public.

Presentation title

subtitle

Name, affiliation

Hosting Institution
City, xx Month xxx

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Title: text

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ENVIRONMENT

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EUROPE

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Blue4all

Title: text

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Blue4all

Figure 2 The template pages of the Power Point Blue4all project

4.4. BLUE4ALL Text Documents

As part of the communication work, a cover page (Figure 3) was developed which will also be used for all external communication.

Figure 3 BLUE4ALL text template cover page

4.5. BLUE4ALL meeting minutes template

As part of BLUE4ALL visual identity, a template was also created to record the minutes of the various meetings held during the project. The template follows the Text Documents template described above, and highlights (both in the text and in the summary) any key actions and decisions that emerged from the meeting.

5. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND ACTIVITIES

To achieve communication and dissemination that effectively meet the project's objectives, BLUE4ALL employs various communication tools and activities using different platforms and instruments to reach diverse target audiences in different contexts, as described below.

5.1. TARGET AUDIENCES

Communication and dissemination activities and materials will be crucial to support the BLUE4ALL project community engagement. The BLUE4ALL target audience is interested in findings with user-friendly guidance for effective, efficient and resilient MPAs and MPA networks. The Blueprint Platform target audiences needs tailored results for European MPAs but also applicable beyond Europe, will hence be to be benefit of all those engaged in MPA processes (e.g. de.g., decision-makers and (sub)national, national, n and global levels; economic actors benefitting from healthy coastal and marine ecosystems like fishers, tourism, and renewable energy operators). BLUE4ALL results will be of direct benefit to (1) the Stakeholder Engagement Groups established for each of the **14 Living Labs and 11 Information Sites** (cfr D4.3) and (2) those engaged in MPA processes beyond the BLUE4ALL consortium. The latter will be facilitated by the establishment of the Blue Parks network (cfr D6.3), ensuring the legacy of BLUE4ALL and hence, its contribution to restoring our oceans and waters.

The main target groups for the communication and dissemination activities are identified below:

- **Scientific community** - to share knowledge and expertise across disciplines, promote future research, and inform about the project research and outcomes. Ecological tools are used for finding the best areas for MPA extensions and to ensure connectivity within MPA networks.
- **Governments** - to improve the understanding of policy/decision-makers for designation of effective conservation, including the need for guidelines and standards, and inform evidence-based policies and management.
- **EU Policymaker's and Member State Policymakers**, including in focus countries.
- **Local Policymakers, public bodies officials, and civil servants** (elected and public officials from authorities at regional/city level).
- **Standards community** - to foster MPA activities in all EU regional seas and ensure the uptake and implementation of standards and guidelines developed in the project.
- **Business sector** - to highlight the benefits of innovative business models in several coastal areas to deliver benefits form the marine ecosystem services for different economic sectors.
- **Journalists** - to increase the visibility and perception as reliable and useful and amplify the societal reach of the project.
- **Citizens** - to raise awareness about MPAs, inform about benefits and value, and promote uptake by society; to provide credible information and encourage a dialogue between science and society.

- **Consortium partners and EC Project Officer** - to ensure effective communication of the project progress.

Some of the target audiences are already part of the wider community, in which case the purpose of the activities is to communicate the project outcomes and foster discussion for reaching consensus and identifying aspects where further research is needed.

5.2. Mapping of local target groups and engagement plan

Engagement plan

In WP4 a stakeholder engagement plan was developed (D4.1) where a **portfolio of stakeholder engagement** tools and guidelines were put together for the future engagement of local stakeholders which will be our specific target groups. Currently, WP4 is working on the methodology for mapping the local stakeholders.

The communication and dissemination to specific target groups will be part of a structured loop created to interact with IS and/or LL and to avoid stakeholder fatigue (Figure 4). The internal workflow consists of six steps:

1. The task leads in WP2 and WP3 prepare information, materials and questions for IS and/or LL assessment.
2. WP2 and WP3 leads collect material from task leads (step 1) and send it to WP4.
3. WP4 task lead concatenates and quality check interaction material from WP2 and WP3 and sends to WP6.
4. **WP6 reviews material and reformulate in line to ease language and make material approachable for a broad range of stakeholders with different knowledge and communication levels.**
5. WP4 task lead is responsible for incorporation of input from WP6 in collaboration with WP2 and WP3. WP4 sends interaction material to contact points.
6. Contact points from IS and/or LL adjusts the material to language and cultural setting if necessary and conduct engagement. Contact points sends gathered information to WP4.

Figure 4. Internal loop of preparation and information handling for the engagement with IS and LL local target groups.

For further details on the timeline, objectives of the interaction, please check “D4.1- Information sites engagement plan - A strategic document to guide and inform intelligence gathering from information sites and living labs, setting the scene and establishing rules of engagement with information providers”.

Mapping of stakeholders

WP4 is currently in the process of setting up the analysis for the upcoming mapping of stakeholders. Considering that the Learning Labs are quite large networks, the analysis of the local target groups will be done by each contact point together with the Living Lab manager in the period **October - end of December 2023**.

Contact Points (CPs) will conduct a guided interview with the **Living Lab Main Contact (LLMC)** where they will identify all existing stakeholder groups in the Living Labs and persons who are the potential representatives. The analysis will be done against various criteria such as interest influence, and others to gain a better understanding of each stakeholder group (Figure 5).

Stakeholder	CRITERIA FOR EVALUATING PRIMARY vs SECONDARY STAKEHOLDERS								SEG member	Technical advisor to SEG	Liaison to stakeholder group	Keep informed
	Existing rights to marine resources	Continuous relationship to marine resources	Unique knowledge of marine resources	Historical/ cultural relationship to resources	Degree of economic and social reliance on resource	Degree of effort and interest in management	Total score	Is this a primary (p) or secondary (s) stakeholder				
STAKEHOLDERS WITH DIRECT CONNECTION TO LIVING LAB												
Group 1												
Group 2												
Group 3												
Group 4												
OTHER STAKEHOLDERS WITH A DIRECT INTEREST												
Group 6												
Group 7												
Group 8												
Group 9												
OTHER USER GROUPS												
Group 10												
Group 11												
Group 12												
Group 13												
Group 14												
Group 15												
INTEREST GROUPS (e.g. local or international NGOs)												
LOCAL COMMUNITY GROUPS												
GOVERNMENT												
OTHER												

Figure 5 Criteria for evaluating each stakeholders group.

The communication and dissemination to be done from WP6 will be back-to-back with, and guided by, the needs from WP2-WP4, especially the CPs.

5.3. Joint Communication and Dissemination Actions

The participation of the consortium in the COMDISS activities are essentials to ensure both project dissemination and constant and/or specific feedback from stakeholders.

Hereafter table 1 is defined of the consortium.

Task, Description, (numbers)	Partner in charge	Contributors	Description of task
6.1 Video (4)	MEDSEA, RBINS, WWF ADRIA, NUID UCD	CMCC & SUB	A video per test network area summarizing activities carried out with each local environment
6.1 Promotional video (1)	SUB	CMCC & all PPs	A video explaining the projects objectives
6.1 Final video (1)	SUB	CMCC & all PPs	A final video with BLUE4ALL achievements
6.4 DEMO Sessions (1 for each Living Labs)	All	SUB & CMCC	An interactive webinar to showcase the firsthand insights from the implementation areas to MPA managers
6.4 DEMO Sessions (1 EU-wide)	RBINS	SUB & CMCC	An interactive webinar to showcase the firsthand insights from the implementation areas to MPA managers
6.5 Events	SUB	CMCC & All PPs	A series of events co-organized to showcase the Living Labs in the context of the Ocean Mission campaign.

Table 1 BLUE4ALL task description and Partner participation

5.4. The KPIs

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) refer to the key elements that can be monitored and used to determine the performance of activities, in this case, related to the dissemination and communication of the project. This measurement contributes to assessing whether the activities are meeting the expected results and can serve as a trigger to implement corrective measures or re-evaluate the objectives. The communication and dissemination KPIs for BLUE4ALL project have been determined using the established parameters of the Grant Agreement and additional measures developed during the creation of the communication and dissemination plan. To adequately measure the success of the overall communication of the project, these KPIs will be periodically monitored. To ensure that KPIs are easy to understand and measure, five core KPIs are usually defined for outreach and engagement.

Channels	KPIs numbers	Numbers as reference
Publications, reports and articles	Publications	8
Scientific publications	Manuscripts	5
Participation in ad hoc events	Participants	30
Joint actions with other EU projects	Actions	5
Website	Visitors	5000/10
Social Media	Followers	500
Newsletter	Subscribers	6/500
Digital/printed flyer	Flyers	3
Press releases / Media participation	Articles	>10
Traveling exhibition	Places where the exhibition takes place	10/1000
Demo and training sessions including for the final Blueprint	Sessions/People reached	5/400
Short Living Lab promo videos for the blueprint and individual labs	Video/Participants	5/1000
Policy infographic and policy recommendations	Documents	5
Project documents (e.g., deliverables, educational material)	Downloads	600
Living labs	Workshops/Participants	8/100

Table 2 Communication Channel and KPIs

In order to track the achievement of KPIs, we have an internal tracker that tell us based on everyone's input, how far away or close we are from achieving them. Even though it is difficult to keep this up to date monthly, this is filled by everyone before the reporting period.

5.5. Online Channels

5.5.1. Website

The BLUE4ALL project website (www.BLUE4ALL.eu) aims at providing information and updates about the topics, activities, and results of the project to a wide range of users, including BLUE4ALL consortium members, end-users, potential users, the scientific community, policymakers, the general public, and the civil society. Online from April 2023, the website is implemented with [Drupal](#), which allows an organization of the content that is highly flexible, and dynamic, and can be adapted to the evolving needs of the project during its activities. In its start-up version, the website is organized into different sections plus the home page.

Home Page

The Home Page was designed to highlight the vision and the mission of the project and the latest information and content that shed light on the more relevant activities and outcomes related to BLUE4ALL. Nevertheless, between October and November 2023, the homepage was redesigned (Figure 6) and the structure reformulated to increase the user friendliness and visual attraction to the page of the project. The graphic concept of the home page is reflected in all the webpages; it is made of a combination of texts, icons, and graphics realised ad hoc for the BLUE4ALL website. The contents of the home page will be enriched with updated and fresh material as the project advances and completes its activities (events, newsletters, deliverables, outcomes, etc.).

Figure 6 BLUE4ALL website: home page redesigned

ABOUT

The ABOUT section was also redesigned and now it includes three subsections (Figure 7):

- BLUE4ALL project
- Partners
- Mission Ocean

Figure 7. New menu from the 'About' section

Blue4all project subpage

The page about BLUE4ALL provides information on the general concept of the project, its structure, and the topics that are the object of the project research, key facts and a BLUE4ALL timeline as it was in the previous version. However, in the new version it now includes a section called “Key Facts” where it explains that it is a project funded under Mission Ocean and where it provides links to the sister projects (Figure 8-10).

Home > About > The Blue4All project

The Blue4All project

BLUE4ALL is a HORIZON Europe Ocean Mission project working towards addressing marine conservation and restoration challenges in Europe. It proposes a new approach to Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) that aligns with EU Biodiversity Strategy and national initiatives. The project places stakeholders at the center of the MPA process, ensuring their needs and concerns are addressed from the outset. BLUE4ALL will work with stakeholders from 25 information sites and Living labs in the Mediterranean Sea, Baltic Sea, and North-East Atlantic regions to develop tools for preserving and restoring the marine environment in a socially sustainable and acceptable way. These tools will be tested in Living labs, and ultimately result in a user-friendly Blueprint Platform for creating effective, efficient, and resilient MPAs and networks of MPAs. The project will run from January 2023 to December 2026.

Figure 8. Blue4all project page, first section

KEY FACTS

Ocean Mission

BLUE4ALL is funded by the [Horizon Europe Mission Ocean](#) and aims to achieving the EU MISSION on Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030.

Duration

The project runs from January 2023 to December 2026.

Living Laboratories and Information sites

Blue4All includes 25 MPAs and MPA networks ([12 Information Sites and 13 Living Labs](#)), from small, coastal MPAs to large MPA networks protecting deep-sea habitats. The sites are located in the Baltic Sea, the Mediterranean Sea and the North-East Atlantic, with an additional site in Brazilian waters to help identify international good practice.

Throughout the project, information sites and Living Labs will provide direct insight in MPA processes, their challenges and solutions. The 13 Living Labs will serve to validate the developed Blueprint Platform for successful co-management of marine protected areas under the kind of geographical (e.g. location, size, habitats and governance (e.g. protection status, degree of stakeholders involvement) conditions representing the majority of MPAs in EU waters.

Partners

The project brings together [22 partners](#) from different institutions from all around Europe (Belgium, France, Italy, Germany, The Netherlands, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Estonia, Montenegro, Croatia, Ireland and Switzerland).

Sister/relevant projects

- [Ocean Citizen](#)
- [PREP4BLUE](#)
- [MSP4BIO](#)

Figure 9. Blue4all project page, second section

Figure 10. Blue4all project page, third section

Partners

It is important to offer the audience the possibility of seeing the team that is behind BLUE4ALL. For this reason, under the partners section, our readers can see listed the names and logo of each organization involved in the consortium, as well as a description of these institutions plus their role in the project (Figure 11).

Partners

	<p>– THE ROYAL BELGIAN INSTITUTE OF NATURAL SCIENCES (RBINS) - Belgium</p> <p>The Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS) is a Federal Scientific Institute developing science-based activities and coordinating the national monitoring of the marine environment and human activities in support of national and international policy in a wide range of areas. As governmental research organization, RBINS provides scientific advice to national, regional sea and the EU level decision-making processes. Areas of expertise include biology, ecology, sedimentology and nature and biodiversity conservation and restoration, but also mathematical modelling of marine processes, remote sensing, and aerial surveillance. The marine activities are concentrated in the Operational Directorate Natural environment (OD Nature), of which the Marine Ecology and Management team (MARECO) has a specific expertise on marine conservation, marine mammals and seabirds, hard substrate benthic fauna, invasive species, and underwater sound, embedded in an ecosystem management context. As coordinator of the BLUE4ALL project, MARECO will be responsible for project coordination and management in addition to contributing to nearly every individual task. MARECO will be the main point of contact for three of the information sites and two of the living labs that will respectively inform and validate the Blueprints for co-created effective, efficient and resilient networks of MPAs.</p>
	<p>+ CENTRO EURO-MEDITERRANEO SUI CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI (CMCC) - Italy</p>
	<p>+ SUBMARINER NETWORK - Germany</p>
	<p>+ SOUTHERN DENMARK UNIVERSITY - SDU, Denmark</p>
	<p>+ FINNISH ENVIRONMENT INSTITUTE - SYKE, Finland</p>
	<p>+ UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERP - UA, Belgium</p>

Figure 11. Partners subsection under the About menu item.

Mission Ocean

A new section was added in the new restructuring of the website, where a whole page is dedicated to explaining what is the Mission Ocean and what is the relation of BLUE4ALL with it. The page also provides links to the portfolio analysis published by the Commission in 2023, both in the dashboard and report versions (Figure 12).

Figure 11. Case studies menu and submenus from where information about each Living Lab and Information Site can be accessed from.

Mission Ocean

What is the Mission?

With a 2030 target, the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters' aims to protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters through research and innovation, citizen engagement and blue investments. The Mission's new approach will address the ocean and waters as one and play a key role in achieving climate neutrality and restoring nature.

Cross-cutting enabling actions will support this objective, in particular broad public mobilisation and engagement and a digital ocean and water knowledge system, known as [Digital Twin Ocean](#).

The Mission supports regional engagement and cooperation through area-based "lighthouses" in major sea/river basins: Atlantic-Arctic, Mediterranean Sea, Baltic-North Sea, and Danube-Black Sea. Mission lighthouses are sites to pilot, demonstrate, develop and deploy the Mission activities across EU seas and river basins

BLUE4ALL and Mission Ocean

There are many projects funded under EU Mission Ocean aiming at achieving altogether the overall goal of restoring our Oceans and Waters by 2030. In 2021, BLUE4ALL was funded with [5 other projects with the 'Projects to protect and restore our ocean and waters' goal](#).

However, there were many others funded for:

- Projects to fight pollution
- Projects to support a sustainable blue economy
- Projects to involve citizens, key allies of the Mission
- Coordination support action for each of the lighthouses of the Mission
- Coordination support action for the Mission in general

Portfolio Analysis

The European Commission has published a [Portfolio Analysis Report](#) identifying over 800 EU-funded projects, from 16 EU funding programmes, contributing to the objectives of the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters". The analysis has been performed with the assistance of 12 independent experts and the projects analysed belong to 16 EU funding programmes. The analysis has produced a [Report](#) and a [Dashboard](#). The Dashboard allows users to interact with the data by visualising and filtering from general to more detailed information, according to specific interests.

Blue4All is contributing to Objective 1a of the mission together with another 150 projects.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016416. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contact: [Privacy Policy](#) | Newsletter | [in](#) [X](#)

Figure 12. Page dedicated to Mission Ocean in BLUE4ALL's website. .

CASE STUDIES

In the restructuring of the website, a new section was added called 'Case Studies' from where a specific page for each Living Lab and Information Site can be accessed from (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Case studies menu and submenus from where information about each Living Lab and Information Site can be accessed from.

Once accessing one of these pages, they all follow the same structure presenting the key info for each marine area, the main pressures facing, the best practices from the site and the contact information (Figure 14).

Sea basin	Country	Habitats: coastal/offshore	Single MPA or MPA network	Designation type	Size (km2)
Mediterranean Sea	Croatia	Coastal	Single MPA	National park	196 km ²

Main pressures on the environment

- Fishing and Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated (IUU) Fishing
- Tourism and recreation

Best practices from this site

A more **business-oriented approach** was taken to ensure marine conservation in this MPA. Local fishers of the area developed specific **fishing tourism**, providing tourists with a traditional fishing experience and educating them on fish gastronomy. This significantly increased their incomes while also enhancing the preservation of the natural environment.

[More information](#)

Contact

World Wildlife Fund Adria
 Kora Dvorski
 kdvorski@wwfadria.org

Figure 14. Example of the structure of a specific page for our Living Labs and Information Sites.

NEWS & EVENTS

The main menu was also restructured to keep together under one same area the news, the calendar of events and the access to past newsletter issues (Figure 15).

Home » News & Events

- News
- Calendar of events
- Newsletter

FRENCH PRESS RELEASE 2023-11-22

Media 24 in it's Environment section published a news piece about the work in BLUE4ALL!

[Learn more](#)

Figure 15. New menu for accessing the news, calendar of events, and past newsletter issues.

The News section is visible from the website (left side of image, Figure 16) where the last news piece published is highlighted, and the list from past news pieces is accessible when accessing the news section directly (right image, Figure 16). This section collects updates on activities and events such as workshops, conferences, etc. This section is populated as BLUE4ALL activities develop during the project; it is intended to keep track of all the initiatives related to the project, or in which the project is involved. The comms team in BLUE4ALL will push for receiving more news from partners on a regular basis so to keep the section updated.

Figure 16. News section in the project website.

Calendar

Listing upcoming relevant events will be crucial to keep our readers informed and engaged with the dynamic landscape of Marine Protected Areas, Ocean Conservation and the Mission Arena. By highlighting these events, we provide valuable opportunities for our audience to participate, network, and contribute to the discussions and initiatives shaping our field. The calendar will highlight when it is BLUE4ALL participating in such events (Figure 17).

ACTUALITES/ NEWS

MedPAN

NOUVELLES DATES À RETENIR !

NEW SAVE THE DATE !

Atelier régional d'échange

27 November

MedPAN Regional experience-sharing workshop on tourism in Mediterranean MPAs

New SAVE THE DATE!

 The upcoming MedPAN Regional experience-sharing workshop and the MedPAN Annual General Assembly will be hosted from 27 November to 1 December 2023 in Hyères, France and online

 Monday, November 27, 2023 - 09:00 - Friday, December 1, 2023 - 17:00

[Learn more](#)

Past events

1st Mission Arena by Blue Mission BANOS 14 November 2023 - 16 November 2023

Inspiring stakeholders across the Baltic and North Sea to make the Blue Economy carbon-neutral & circular by 2030

[Learn more](#)

Figure 17. Calendar of events.

PUBLICATIONS

The Publications section will host all the documents, data, information, and knowledge that will be provided by the BLUE4ALL WPs. This section will contain Journal articles (peer-reviewed articles), policy briefs and project deliverables once approved. It is the repository where users will be able to reach and consult the project outcomes and follow the steps of the research activities, from the methodology to the results. It also hosts media resources and past newsletter issues as shown in figure 18.

Figure 17. Calendar of events.

Figure 18. Publications section

PLATFORMS

The last menu item is the so-called 'Platforms' from where the Networking Platform and the Blueprint Platform will be accessible from (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Platforms menu

Networking platform

The networking platform is a LinkedIn group dedicated to the BLUE4ALL project aimed at being a forum for professionals to facilitate the dialogue within and across the test sites and allow effective exchange between MPA managers and their key stakeholders for the development of Living Labs. A plan will be put together to motivate each Learning Lab leader to promote it among their relevant stakeholders.

Blueprint platform

This section will be the main entry point to the Blueprint platform for achieving effective, efficient and resilient (networks of) MPAs/OECMs. Actors and stakeholders from the different Living Lab countries will be invited together with experts from within the consortium to discuss the content and format of the perfect user-friendly blueprint for effective, efficient and resilient MPAs and MPA networks. Based on the experience of the partners and users that will be engaged, the blueprint's main functionalities will be identified on user requirements. The blueprint will be designed using an interactive framework in which users and stakeholders will co-design and co-develop it together with technical, scientific and experts (e.g. MPA managers)

5.5.2. Newsletter

In today's fast-paced world of information, it's important to choose strategies that not only maximize the impact of our efforts but also allow us to share excellent value. This is why the BLUE4ALL and MSP4BIO projects have chosen to collaborate on a **joint newsletter strategy** and publication of newsletter issues, more specifically due to:

- **Preventing Stakeholder Fatigue:** We recognize that our stakeholders are inundated with information from multiple sources. By consolidating our updates and insights into one newsletter, we aim to prevent 'stakeholder fatigue,' where important messages might get lost or overlooked in the flood of communications. This consolidation ensures that our information remains focused, relevant, and impactful
- **Avoid dividing audiences:** Our projects share a common thread – a commitment to marine conservation, planning, the protection of biodiversity, and the advancement of the Mission Ocean goals. If we were to divide our audience, we would risk fragmenting the community that shares these interests.
- **Boosting Cooperation Among Projects:** Collaboration is at the heart of the Mission Ocean's interest and of successful conservation efforts. By joining forces for this newsletter, we encourage closer cooperation between BLUE4ALL, MSP4BIO, and sister projects that will be featured in each newsletter. This not only facilitates the exchange of knowledge and best practices but also sparks new ideas and synergies that can further our individual and collective objectives.
- **Efficient Use of Resources:** Both projects have allocated economic resources to communication and dissemination activities. By pooling these resources for the joint newsletter, we can make more effective use of our budgets. It's a strategic choice that allows us to achieve more with less.

In conclusion, our decision to create a joint newsletter is not just about convenience – it's a strategic move that amplifies our collective voice, avoids audience fragmentation, fosters cooperation, and maximizes the impact of our communication efforts. Together, we are better positioned to drive positive change in the realms of Marine Protected Areas, Maritime Spatial Planning, and Ocean Conservation.

Blue Horizons

The joint newsletter will be called, “Blue Horizons”, a name carefully chosen to encapsulate our shared vision. Just as the horizon stretches beyond our sight, so too do the opportunities for collaboration among

stakeholders, among projects, the opportunities for marine conservation, for doing better spatial planning and for having general positive change for our Ocean. “Blue Horizons” embodies our commitment to exploring these horizons together, charting a sustainable course for the future of our oceans.

Figure 20 shows the cover for the first issue to be released in September 2023.

The main sections of the newsletter will be:

1. **Issue introduction** - Including an introduction in each newsletter issue will be essential for several reasons. Firstly, it offers context, helping readers understand the purpose and relevance of the content they're about to explore. Secondly, it acts as a point of connection, reminding our audience of the overarching goals we share among both BLUE4ALL & MSP4BIO. Ultimately, an introduction serves as a welcoming entry point, ensuring that our readers feel informed, involved, and connected to our community's ongoing efforts.

2. **Updates from BLUE4ALL** – We will highlight the latest happenings in the project. These could be activities carried out, deliverables published, events attended, available resources, website updates, calls to action, synergies created, and more.

Figure 21 shows a screenshot of the updates in the first issue.

Figure 20. Blue Horizons' cover and introduction for issue#1

Figure 21 BLUE4ALL updates section in the Blue Horizons newsletter issue#1

3. **Updates from MSP4BIO** – The content will be the same type as in number 2 but with activities related to the [MSP4IO project](#).

Figure 22 shows a screenshot of the updates in the first issue.

Figure 22. MSP4BIO updates section in the Blue Horizons newsletter issue#1

4. **Upcoming relevant events** – We will list the upcoming events relevant to our audience, which are also in line with MSP4BIO and BLUE4ALL projects' topics. Figure 23 shows a screenshot of how this section will look like in Blue Horizons.

Figure 23. Events section in the Blue Horizons newsletter issue#1

5. **Announcements** – This section will be used for posting opportunities that could be of interest to our audience, as well as having calls to action. In the Blue Horizons issue #1, an announcement will be made for a postdoctoral opportunity to join BLUE4ALL project (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Announcements section in the Blue Horizons newsletter issue#1

6. **Sister project features** – This last section will give the opportunity to other relevant projects working in the same topics of interest as us, to publish news relevant to our audience. Specifically, the projects [Ocean Citizen](#), [MPA Europe](#), and [MarinePlan](#).

Figure 25. Sister project features section in the Blue Horizons newsletter issue#1

5.5.3. Video

A video giving the overview of the project was produced to present it at the European Maritime Day 2023 and it is now being displayed at the home page of BLUE4ALL's website or directly through this link: https://www.blue4all.eu/sites/blue4all.eu/files/managed/Videos/BLUE4ALL_720p.mp4

Figure 26. Video Blue4all

Along the project, more videos will be created to highlight the pilot sites and its achievements.

5.5.4. Social Media Channels

Social media are valuable platforms for the dissemination and communication of content produced through scientific research. In particular, they are functional for the broader circulation of messages within the scientific community and for better dissemination of research results outside the community of peers, especially to groups interested in the BLUE4ALL topics, such as the project stakeholders.

Moreover, a further function of social media for a research project such as BLUE4ALL is to activate and initiate relationships with potentially interested parties with activities/interests similar to those of the project. As they enable dialogue between accounts related to research projects, institutions (local/national/European/global), and individuals, social media are the right place to develop and maintain relations that can lead to useful insights.

BLUE4ALL has identified two social media platform suitable for its communication and dissemination activities:

- **LinkedIn**

LinkedIn Page

LinkedIn will be used primarily for professional relations. Communication via the BLUE4ALL group will target professionals and other organisations involved in research areas akin to those of BLUE4ALL. The LinkedIn group will also post materials shared through PP's social media and the website to stimulate social interaction and the dissemination of BLUE4ALL key messages and activities. Thus, the content to be published has to be **related to BLUE4ALL's events and activities, as well as a redirector to our website's content.**

Figure 27. Example of post in Blue4all's LinkedIn

An example of this would be posting the **events** we attend to, the **people** we are in talks with, the **activities** we are organizing, the **take-on** from a conference, the fruitful **connections** from networking events we were at.

An example of this would be to post about attending the European Maritime Day 23 (Figure 27).

Until August 2023, the LinkedIn page of BLUE4ALL counts 84 followers.

LinkedIn Group

The LinkedIn group dedicated to the BLUE4ALL project is a forum for professionals which will facilitate the dialogue within and across the test sites and allow effective exchange between MPA managers and their key stakeholders for the development of Living Labs. It will operate as an MPA Network Knowledge Transfer Platform, mainly targeting the MPA managers, to allow

communication along the network and engagement of different audiences to support MPA managers engage with different stakeholders – tourism, fisheries, etc.

BLUE4ALL project works on strengthening the MPA networks by mapping the key influential actors and developing specific strategies to intensify the dialogue in each of the networks. To this purpose, the MPA Networking Platform can operate both locally for the concrete MPA and among MPA managers of different locations to exchange experiences. It is used to develop specific Living Labs, stimulate interaction and responsive participation, and enhance communication between different Living Labs.

This networking platform allows for live chat, video conferences and webinars, as well as sharing of documents. The platform is developed as a restricted access area, available only to BLUE4ALL MPA managers and associated stakeholders.

The LinkedIn Group has currently 12 members, which is expected considering that we are not at the stage of the project where the local target groups have been defined (see 5.1). Considering that the LinkedIn Groups is meant for local stakeholders, we will start populating this group in 2025 when we start working with the mapped local groups.

- **Twitter**

Twitter is a fast-paced platform that allows the user to consume fast, concisely and to the point. Furthermore, it allows the audience to see what's trending in their social world. Different to LinkedIn's audience, the advantage of Twitter is that it **doesn't only have the average consumer, but also journalists, politicians and celebrities** (83% of the world's leaders are on Twitter according to Sprouts Social, 2018) that keep the platform ideal to find and consume the trending news.

Therefore, BLUE4ALL's Twitter strategy will be more dynamic, posting a couple of times per week and sharing not only information from the project, but also information relevant to our target audience of topics related to BLUE4ALL's. More specifically:

- Tweets related to the project – This means news from BLUE4ALL and its activities.
- Tweets relevant for the project – These are tweets of relevant news, events, trending topics, etc., that relate to BLUE4ALL's interests, but that are not an outcome of our project. For example, a new report on co-development practices for MPAs, an event related to marine protected areas, a piece of news of success stories for networks of MPAs, among others.
- Retweets from relevant accounts– This will be used for bringing to our audience existing content that is relevant for them. It also helps build up our project's community as they can see we could be a good information provider on MPAs.
- Quote relevant original tweets– When possible and relevant, quote the original tweet instead of retweeting it. This will be helpful when we want to add extra information on what is been already said or when we want to give an opinion on it.

]

Example of retweet with quote:

Figure 28. Example of a tweet in BLUE4ALL's X account.

Relevant accounts

It is key to tag relevant accounts in our tweets. For example, if a photo is published, tag the people/projects appearing in it. This will make them share our tweet and reach a broader audience. If not a photo, mention relevant accounts on the tweet.

Accounts to keep in mind:

→ AGENCIES

[@HorizonEU](#), [@cinea_eu](#), [@EUClimateAction](#), [@EUScienceInnov](#), [@EU_Commission](#), [@EU_MARE](#), [@EUEnvironment](#)

→ CONSORTIUM

[@RBINSmuseum](#), [@CmccClimate](#), [@SubmNet](#), [@NATsdu](#), [@SYKEint](#), [@UAntwerpen](#), [@ucddublin](#), [@udepalermo](#), [@unitartu](#), [@TUP1632](#), [@VLIZnews](#), [@HELCOMInfo](#), [@IUCN](#), [@IUCN_Water](#), [@WWF_Baltic](#), [@WWF_Med](#), [@WWFMed](#), [@ICES_ASC](#), [@WUR](#), [@medsea_f](#), [@OFBiodiversite](#).

→ PEOPLE IN THE CONSORTIUM

[@mirtazupan](#), [@Ivannah_S](#), [@marianaml_mar](#), [@CintiaOQuintana](#), [@HaslerSheetal](#), [@fiske_cecilie](#), [@rvarjopuro](#), [@geertjeschuite1](#), [@FR_Barboza](#), [@Iiisilees](#), [@EveraertGert](#), [@Fien_dr](#), [@SchepersLennert](#), [@JannicaHaldin](#), [@SebValanko](#), [@FRAFRAU81](#), [@Giulia_Eremita](#).

→ OTHER RELEVANT PEOPLE/ACCOUNTS

[@eumissionocean](#), [@Vsinkevicius](#) (Commissioner for Environment, Oceans and Fisheries).

5.5.5. Partners' Channels

A significant part of BLUE4ALL's communication outreach potential relates to the ability to engage the consortium partners' channels, tools, and networks to maximise message dissemination and intensify relationships with target groups. For example, institutional websites, social media, media relations, webinars, and events are all part of the BLUE4ALL communication plan having a consistent role in the communication strategies of the project partners and are opportunities to intensify and enhance the communication capacity of the project (Figure 29).

The screenshot shows the HELCOM website. The top navigation bar includes links for Home, Contact us, Vacancies, News & Media, Publications, Data & Maps, and Meeting portal. Below this is a secondary navigation bar with links for About us, HELCOM at work, Baltic Sea knowledge, Action areas, and Baltic Sea Action Plan. A third navigation bar lists Groups, Projects, Ministerial meetings, Events, News & Media, Publications, and Recommendations. On the left, a 'Projects' sidebar lists various ongoing projects, with 'BLUE4ALL' highlighted. The main content area features the title 'BLUE4ALL' and a sub-headline 'Blueprint demonstration for co-created effective, efficient and resilient networks of MPAs'. The text describes the project's mission to address challenges in marine conservation and restoration in Europe, its approach of co-creation with stakeholders, and the use of Living Labs. A cookie consent banner is visible at the bottom of the page.

Figure 29. Example of an article about BLUE4ALL being published in a partner's channel.

5.6. Press Releases

A Press Release will be developed for each activity with high public relevance (meetings, outcomes, publications, etc.). Press releases will be published on the website and delivered to the media contact list to reach out to local/national/EU media and get appropriate coverage, thus contributing to raising awareness among the communities interested in the outcomes of the project. Press releases will be in English and translations in the partners' national languages will be available also through the partners' websites.

Since there are no main achievements yet, we prepared a general press release about the project (Figure 30) to be used and adapted by partners who would find it interesting. In Figure 31 it can be seen how our partner OFB (Office français de la biodiversité) distributed it to a French media channel called Media 24.

Press Release

BLUE4ALL Project: Co-Creating Effective, Efficient, and Resilient Marine Protected Areas for Biodiversity Conservation

Place, Date

The BLUE4ALL project, a groundbreaking initiative focused on the co-creation of effective, efficient, and resilient networks of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), is set to revolutionize marine biodiversity conservation and restoration efforts. The project aims to align top-down regulatory demands with bottom-up societal expectations, bridging the gap between policy objectives and stakeholder engagement.

The urgency to strengthen marine conservation and restoration globally has prompted the need for comprehensive strategies and innovative solutions. The BLUE4ALL project recognizes this imperative and leverages the power of collaboration and co-creation to address the challenges faced in the MPA process.

At the heart of BLUE4ALL is the belief that successful conservation outcomes are best achieved when stakeholders are actively involved from the early stages of MPA design, management, and enforcement. The project establishes direct connections with 25 Information Sites and Living Labs, ensuring a tangible link to the field of MPAs and networks of MPAs across Europe. By leveraging real-world examples, the project aims to not only understand the challenges encountered but also co-develop and test new solutions where needed.

The ultimate outcome of the BLUE4ALL project will be the interactive Blueprint Platform—a guide to effective, efficient, and resilient (networks of) MPAs. This platform, applicable not only at the pan-European level but also beyond the EU, will serve as a beacon of guidance to support EU leadership in international efforts to combat marine biodiversity loss.

"We believe that the key to successful marine conservation lies in aligning regulatory expectations with the aspirations of local communities and stakeholders," said Steven Degraer, Coordinator of BLUE4ALL and Senior Environmental Scientist at Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences. "BLUE4ALL will pave the way for a new era of co-creation and collaboration in designing and managing MPAs, ensuring the preservation and responsible use of our precious marine ecosystems."

The BLUE4ALL project is driven by the need to reach and surpass global targets for protecting terrestrial and marine areas. The EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 sets a clear objective of legally protecting at least 30% of the land and sea in the EU, with one-third under strict protection. However, current assessments indicate that the European MPA network falls short of ecological targets and faces challenges such as small sizes, inadequate management, and enforcement.

By embracing a bottom-up approach and integrating stakeholders throughout the MPA process, BLUE4ALL aims to overcome these challenges and contribute to the restoration of our oceans and waters. The project aligns with the United Nations Decade of the Oceans 2021-2030, UN Decade of Ecosystem Restoration 2021-2031, and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, particularly Sustainable Development Goal 14 on the conservation and sustainable use of oceans, seas, and marine resources.

BLUE4ALL will actively engage with relevant services, initiatives, and infrastructures such as EMODNET, Copernicus Marine Service, Lifewatch, and the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), ensuring the utilization of cutting-edge technologies and knowledge.

With BLUE4ALL, a new era of collaborative marine conservation is on the horizon. By empowering stakeholders and co-creating effective solutions, the project aspires to make a significant contribution to preserving our oceans and their invaluable biodiversity.

For more information about the BLUE4ALL project, visit <https://www.blue4all.eu/> or contact our communications officer at mml@submariner-network.eu.

About [Local Partner Organization] [Local Partner Organization] is a [brief description of your organization's mission, expertise, or role in the project].

Local Press Contact:

Name: [redacted]
 Title: [redacted]
 Phone: [redacted]
 Email: [redacted]

Blueprint demonstration for co-created effective, efficient, and resilient networks of MPAs.

Twitter: @BLUE4ALLproject
 LinkedIn: @Blue4all

Figure 30. Press release drafted and distributed among partners.

Actualités Economies Entreprises Environnement High-Tech Sports Tendances Portraits

Environnement

BLUE4ALL : Vers une nouvelle ère de conservation marine grâce à la cocréation

Publié par: Eric GARLETTI | Date: 18 octobre 2023

En plein cœur des défis planétaires actuels, la préservation de la biodiversité marine est devenue une urgence. Face à cela, l'Europe lance le projet BLUE4ALL, une initiative innovante axée sur la cocréation pour renforcer la conservation marine. Nous plongeons dans les détails et les aspirations de ce projet ambitieux.

Cocréation : Le mot-clé pour une conservation réussie

Les aires marines protégées (AMP) représentent un enjeu majeur pour la préservation de nos écosystèmes marins. BLUE4ALL, en reconnaissant l'importance de ces zones, vise à améliorer leur gestion et leur création en misant sur une implication forte des parties prenantes dès les premiers pas du processus. Ainsi, les gestionnaires d'AMP, les communautés locales, et les diverses parties prenantes travaillent main dans la main pour concevoir et animer ces zones protégées. C'est dans cette optique que BLUE4ALL a établi des liens avec 25 AMP ou réseaux d'AMP en Europe.

Blueprint : La plateforme pour l'avenir des AMP

L'aboutissement du projet BLUE4ALL se manifestera à travers la plateforme interactive "Blueprint". Cette dernière servira de véritable carrefour pour le partage de connaissances et de solutions testées en conditions réelles durant le projet. Plus qu'un simple outil paneuropéen, Blueprint ambitionne d'avoir une portée internationale, soutenant ainsi les efforts globaux contre la perte de biodiversité marine.

Les ambitions à l'horizon 2030

L'Union européenne a déjà fixé des objectifs clairs pour 2030 : protéger juridiquement au moins 30% de ses terres et mers. Toutefois, les AMP actuels font face à de nombreux défis, tels que leur petite taille ou encore une gestion inadéquate. BLUE4ALL, en intégrant une approche ascendante et en plaçant les parties prenantes au cœur du processus, aspire à répondre à ces défis.

Une cohérence avec les agendas mondiaux

Le projet BLUE4ALL ne se limite pas aux frontières européennes en matière d'aspirations. Il est en parfaite harmonie avec plusieurs initiatives mondiales, notamment la Décennie des Nations Unies pour la restauration des écosystèmes et l'objectif de développement durable 14 de l'ONU.

Technologies et collaborations pour un impact maximal

Afin d'optimiser ses actions, BLUE4ALL mise sur la collaboration avec des entités et infrastructures de renom, tels que EMODnet, le Copernicus Marine Service, et le Digital Twin of the Ocean. Le but ? Utiliser les technologies et les connaissances de pointe pour une mise en œuvre réussie des actions de conservation.

Avec le projet BLUE4ALL, l'Europe donne le ton pour une conservation marine du futur, plus collaborative, plus technologique et surtout, plus efficace. Seul l'avenir nous dira si ce pari audacieux portera ses fruits, mais une chose est certaine : la voie de la cocréation semble être la bonne.

TAGS Nature

Figure 31. Press release published in a French media outlet called Media 24. The website to visit it is <https://media24.fr/2023/10/18/blue4all-vers-une-nouvelle-ere-de-conservation-marine-grace-a-la-cocreation/>

5.7. Networking Activities and Synergies

BLUE4ALL will make use of links to other projects through its partners to further promote the project activities. In addition, informal liaisons and information sharing through the existing contacts and related projects of the consortium partners will support the wider diffusion of BLUE4ALL project activities.

BLUE4ALL will leverage the collaboration and synergies with relevant EU-funded projects, initiatives and clusters, projects as described above in relation to the newsletter. The activities involving sister projects will set up a common framework for similar research initiatives and maximise the communication efforts and opportunities of each of them within the cluster system. BLUE4ALL's sister project Ocean Citizen, together with the following projects have agreed to cooperate with BLUE4LL. Their relevance is explained below:

1. [MSP4BIO](#) – The “*Improved Science-Based Maritime Spatial Planning To Safeguard And Restore Biodiversity In A Coherent European MPA Network*” project develops and demonstrates the ways in which knowledge-based Marine Spatial Planning becomes a vehicle and a tool for the protection and recovery of marine ecosystems. It engages MSP planners and MPA managers to develop an integrated flexible socio-ecological management and validate its concrete applicability in 6 pilot sites in 5 European Sea Basins.
2. [Ocean Citizen](#) – The “*Marine Forest coastal restoration: an underwater gardening socio-ecological plan*” project will implement and scale up an advanced regeneration program that joins ecological perspectives with societal commitment, providing clear economic benefits and improving resilience of the local communities.
3. [MPA Europe](#) – The “*Marine Protected Areas Europe*” project will systematically map an optimal network of marine protected areas (MPAs) in all European seas that include as high a biodiversity of species, habitats and ecosystems as possible, and blue carbon stores.
4. [MarinePlan](#) - The “*Improved transdisciplinary science for effective ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning and conservation in European Seas*” project will support the implementation of ecosystem-based MSP through the development of a decision support platform.

The already planned joint activities/actions include but won't be limited to:

Activity	Whom	Why	When
Sister project and other relevant projects' news feature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ocean Citizen • MPA Europe • MarinePlan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common interests related to marine conservation, planning and restoration. • Sharing audiences • Boosting impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • September 2023 issue • January 2024 issue • May 2024 issue • September 2024 issue • January 2025 issue • May 2024 issue • September 2024 issue ... etc
Organization of the workshop “ <i>Safeguarding Biodiversity: Strengthening Marine Protected Area Networks, policy coherence and</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MSP4BIO project 	To discuss the current state and actions in place, challenges, needs and opportunities to support protection and restoration of marine biodiversity and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • November 14-16th, 2023 in Gothenburg, Sweden

<p><i>community involvement</i>” at the 1st Mission BANOS Arena to be held in Gothenburg in November 2023</p>		<p>achievement of 2030 targets. Discussion will be focused on Ocean Mission priorities such as designation of strictly protected areas, creation of MPA networks, integration of MPAs & MSP, and active community involvement.</p>	
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5.8. Synergies with Mission Ocean and Implementation platform

The BLue4ALL partners will engage in communication activities for the EU Mission Restore our Ocean & Waters (Mission Ocean) in a variety of roles, including as speakers at webinars and events, and promotion of diverse opportunities that the Mission Ocean offers. Mission Ocean is promoted via Blue4ALL’s social media channels, including newsletters. Blue4ALL also highlights Mission Ocean-specific future research and policy needs in relevant publications making links to the Mission Ocean objectives and enablers.

The Blue4ALL partners are planning to:

- endorse the [Mission Ocean Charter](#) and pledge actions that will contribute to the successful implementation of the Mission.
- participate in the [Mission Ocean implementation platform](#)
- communicate the BLUE4ALL event in the [Mission Ocean Events platform](#)

A dedicated space will be created on the Blue4ALL website to allow joining the Mission Ocean Charter to help achieve the three objectives of the Mission Ocean, as well as a dedicated footer space.

5.9. Scientific Publications

The strong scientific credentials of Blue4all partners and tools will be exploited by targeting high profile journals for publishing the project’s scientific outcomes. Scientific publications based on project methodologies, processes, and results will be published as open access: an approach to the scientific process based on open cooperative work, tools and diffusing knowledge

Journal papers will present the most significant project results at the highest scientific standards and disseminate them to a scientific audience. As they typically involve long time-to-publish periods, these publications will focus on substantial, matured, and empirically verified project results and are thus more likely to appear towards the project end. No journal papers have been published so far, but some are in preparation.

Relevant target journals include:

- Frontiers in Marine Science
- Limnology and Oceanography Letters
- Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews

- Reviews in Aquaculture
- Reviews in Fisheries Science and Aquaculture
- Marine Pollution Bulletin
- Ocean and Coastal Management
- Frontiers in Marine Science

Conference papers will present fresh interim project results of appropriate scientific quality in a timely manner to disseminate them as quickly as possible in the scientific community. Relevant target conferences and workshops include:

- The European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly
- The Ocean Sciences Meeting
- The European Maritime Days
- The Ocean Forum
- The UN Ocean Decade Conference

5.10. Timeline

Some of the key communication outputs are featured in this Gantt chart. The list includes only the activities for which the timeline has been already defined. The time of delivery is marked in dark blue; the time of preparation, use, or updates – in light blue.

Months	3	6	9	12	18	24	36	48
Logo	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
Website	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
Social account	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
Roll up	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
General template	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
Flyer	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
Communication plan	Light Blue	Dark Blue	White	White	White	White	White	White
Press release	White	White	Light Blue					
Newsletter	White	White	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
General video	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
Events in LL	White	White	Light Blue					

